

ASSESSMENT OF INDIVIDUAL TYPOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ANIMALS IN THE EXPERIMENTAL MODEL OF DIABETES

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Annotation

An individual-typological approach to the body's response to the disease and its complications can facilitate many issues of pathophysiology, pathochemistry and pharmacokinetics, especially in diabetes mellitus. There are quite a few studies around the terrible complications of this disease, associated with impaired microcirculation, often leading to disability and death. Among the pathologies that lead to serious, irreversible microcirculation dysfunctions, the main role is given to diabetes mellitus, which is the most widespread condition studied. Despite continuous long-term research, the use of new modern methods of treatment and diagnosis, the disease continues to progress, not only in countries with high urbanization, but also in countries of average living standards. In modern experimental diabetology, chemical models of diabetes mellitus occupy the first place, and in the field of entopharmacology, various methods of experimental modeling of diabetes mellitus are used. Alloxan diabetes is caused by the administration of alloxan to animals, which selectively necrotizes the islets of the pancreas, followed by the development of classic symptoms of diabetes mellitus. The predominance of the activity of some brain structures over others determines the typological properties of the nervous system, assessing the reaction of the whole organism. The study of the disease with an approach to individual typological features of behavior will allow us to better understand the mechanisms of adaptive responses and identify new differentiated approaches to the prevention and treatment of various diseases, in particular diabetes mellitus and its complications.

Relevance

Diabetes mellitus is a potentially widespread disease worldwide, and the disease is a major health concern. It is currently an incurable metabolic disease that

affects approximately 2.8% of the world's population. The study of individual typological characteristics of the response of the central nervous system (CNS) of humans and animals to the influence of environmental factors and the mechanisms of disease occurrence is one of the most urgent problems among medical and biological sciences today. In recent decades, a special place in research has been occupied by resistance in terms of the body's resistance to the effects of physical and emotional stressors, which determine an individual set of defense mechanisms against stress. An individual-typological approach to the body's response to the disease and its complications can alleviate many issues of pathophysiology, pathochemistry and pharmacokinetics, especially in diabetes. There are many studies about the terrible complications of this disease, which are associated with microcirculation disorders, often leading to disability and death.

The pathophysiology of the microcirculatory system has become a complex and urgent task of medicine, since it covers the smallest diameter (from 2 to 200 microns), functionally interacting and interconnected blood and lymph vessels that ensure the homeostasis of the whole organism. It plays a role in the metabolic mechanisms of life processes, including oxygen consumption, not only at the systemic level, but also at the local level. The main forms of dysfunction in the microcirculation system are of interest to more researchers in different specialties, including physicians, pathophysiologicals, medical physicists, and biologists. Improving the methods of studying the activity and pathological state of microvessels is a necessary direction for a deep understanding of the essence of the pathological state of organs and systems in theoretical and practical medicine. Live study of the tissue microcirculation system in vivo does not always provide a deep understanding of the changes that occur in certain diseases, besides, classical functional diagnostic methods are always incomplete due to the lack of necessary equipment in practical medicine. It is worth noting that the use of high-tech methods to study the microcirculation system joint pathologies, in particular, diabetes, hypertension, vascular atherosclerosis, as well as the body's dependence on blood circulation, types of the central nervous system and menopause conditions, living conditions are always does not show the true picture of his pathological condition. Among the pathologies that lead to serious, irreversible dysfunctions of microcirculation, diabetes, which is the most common condition studied, plays a leading role. Despite continuous long-term research and the use of new modern methods of treatment and diagnosis, the disease continues to develop not only in countries with a high level of

urbanization, but also in countries with an average standard of living. Its prevalence in the world is between 5% and 6% and it tends to increase especially in people over 40 years of age. According to the WHO, the number of patients with diabetes has doubled in the last 10 years and is approximately 160 million, and by 2025, their number is projected to double, and this increase is accompanied by patients with type 2 diabetes. depends. In modern experimental diabetology, chemical models of diabetes occupy the first place, and according to the literature, various methods of experimental model of diabetes were used in the field of enteropharmacology from 1996 to 2006. Thus, streptozotocin was used in 69% of cases and alloxan in 31% of cases. Among the chemical models, streptozotocin and alloxan are the most common drugs used to induce experimental diabetes. Streptozotocin (streptozocin, isostocin, zanozar) is a synthetic drug obtained from *Streptomyces achromogenes* microorganisms, hence the name. Alloxan diabetes is caused by the administration of alloxan to animals, which develops necrotic processes in the pancreas and develops the first symptoms of diabetes.

Chervova I.V. (2007) proved the connection between the nature of behavioral reactions and vegetative parameters depending on the individual typological reactions of the organism.

Pritvorova A.V. in his scientific study (2018) he was able to prove that rats with individual typological behavioral characteristics (ITXX) in the T-shaped maze have different indicators of the level of oxidative modification of protein and the activity of antioxidant enzymes in the norm.

Experimental diabetology is of great importance for the identification, treatment and prevention of pathogenic problems of the disease. Experimental diabetology provides information not only for understanding pathophysiology, but also for studying the mechanism of action of antidiabetic drugs. To date, there are several models of experimental diabetes, the main ones are:

1. Surgical model. Complete (total) or partial (subtotal) removal of the pancreas.
2. Chemical model. Chemical substances that have a selective effect on cells: alloxan, streptozocin, dithizon, etc.
3. Endocrine model. Long-term administration of adenohipophysis, somatotropic hormones, ACTG, and glucocorticoids induces diabetes
4. Immune model. As a result of the introduction of anti-insulin antibodies into the stomach.
5. Genetic model. Induction of hereditary diabetes in mice and other animals

Thus, Russian and European scientists analyzed the literature and came to the opinion that the body's reactions to the pathogenesis, manifestation of clinical forms, complications, treatment and prevention of the development of the disease should be approached from an individual typological point of view.

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